

Measurement of Tractive Rolling of the Fingertip

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Abstract. Stable contact is essential for dexterous object manipulation, as it enables reliable force transmission and prevents unwanted slip. When subjected to tangential loading, the contact interface is subjected to localized partial slip but the contact interface also shift along the fingertip surface, a phenomenon known as tractive rolling. While fingertip rolling could provide additional manual compliance and may contribute to grip stability, it remains poorly quantified.

To address this gap, we used a state-of-the-art imaging system to experimentally characterize the fingertip rolling under progressive tangential loading. Preliminary results indicated that rolling dynamics was significantly influenced by both the direction of the tangential loading and the applied normal force. Ongoing work will examine the relationship between tractive rolling and slip dynamics, with the aim of clarifying its functional role in contact stabilization during manipulation.

Keywords: Fingertip mechanics · Friction · Digital Image Correlation.

1 Introduction

The fingertip is grossly composed of a rigid bone structure, soft biological tissues and surrounding skin anchored to the bone by collagen fibers. Histological observations show that these fibers align radially when stretched which act as to keep the surface of the fingertip close to the bone [1]. However when manipulating objects, the fingertip still sustain important geometric changes and the skin naturally rotate around the bone. This rolling induced by tangential force or tractive rolling, makes the contact interface shifts around fingertip skin patches (also referred to peeling mechanism [2]). While this phenomenon has large implications onto the stability of the contact and is often talked about in discussion sections [3–5], no quantification characterization of this phenomenon on the fingertip is known by the authors.

Using a imaging method tracking the displacement of the fingertip surface, we will quantify how tractive rolling scale to normal force, lateral speed and tangential loading direction. More specifically we will test normal force in the range of 0.5 N to 10 N, lateral speed between 1 mm/s to 20 mm/s, and tangential plate direction in the ulnar-radial axis.

2 Methods and Results

Experimental approach used in this work were validated in previous studies focusing on the surface strain of the fingertip [6, 7]. Five volunteers participated in the experiment and provided written informed consent. The experiment was approved by the local ethics committee (reference 2025/03NOV/451, Comité d’Ethique Hospitalo-Facultaire de Saint-Luc - UCLouvain).

Mechanical stimulation The index fingertip of human participants was passively pressed against a flat surface with a maintained normal force of either 0.5 N to 10 N. The surface was then translated horizontally in either the ulnar or radial, distal, or proximal direction at a constant speed (Fig.1A)

Reconstruction and rolling measurement Stereo digital image correlation (3D-DIC) was used to track artificial features on the skin using multiple cameras (Fig.1B). This produced a time-resolved 3D surface of the fingerpad (Fig.1C). A band aligned along the ulnar-radial axis and centered on the fingertip’s contact area was defined. Using this band, a segment was created by connecting its highest points on either side. The rolling angle of the fingertip was then determined by measuring the change in orientation of this segment relative to the fingertip initial state (Fig.1D).

Preliminary results show that ulnar and radial direction create pronounced tractive rolling, largely shifting the contact (Fig.1E). Rolling angle linearly increases with lateral position and scale with normal force applied (Fig.1F).

3 Future perspectives

We aim to investigate the rolling mechanism in the perspective of contact stability, i.e. along with partial slip evolution.

Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange Our quantitative characterization of passive tractive rolling in the human fingertip opens direct questions for the robotics community. In robotic manipulation, rolling is deliberately exploited as a high-dexterity technique, allowing continuous reorientation of a grasped object without breaking contact. This passive rolling documented here, a consequence of soft tissue mechanics under tangential loading remains unaccounted for. We invite roboticists and contact mechanics specialists to discuss how our measurements of rolling could inform the design of biomimetic robotic fingertips and improve slip prediction in tactile control loops.

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Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Fig. 1. Overview of the measurement methods and analysis. (A) Setup composed of an imaging apparatus and a robotic platform to passively engage the human fingertip. (B) Exemplar image of the fingertip from cam#1 with zoom view of the ink pattern. (C) 3D surface reconstruction of the fingertip before and after contact, and following a plate traction in the radial direction. (D) Illustration of the tractive rolling measurement. (E) Maps of fingertip before and after tractive rolling in four direction of plate stimulation. (F) Evolution of tractive rolling with lateral position of the plate stimulation for one subject. Effect of normal force conditions is shown at 1 N (cross markers) and at 5 N (point markers). Color code for each direction is defined as in E. Figure panels A to C are used with permission from [7].

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